

BfR answers questions of the Bundestag Committee on Food, Agriculture and Consumer Protection

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The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) has answered questions regarding nutrient profiles posed by the Committee on Food, Agriculture and Consumer Protection of the German Bundestag. The Committee has requested the opinions of different experts and interest groups on the issue of nutrient profiles as put forth in the European Regulation on Nutrition and Health Claims made on foods. These were presented at a public hearing on 6 October 2010.

According to Article 4 of Regulation (EC) No 1924/2006, certain nutrient profiles govern the circumstances in which health claims may be made in regard to food. Nutrient profiles are meant to ensure that foods advertised to have a positive health effect are not also rich in nutrients which are linked with chronic illness if they are consumed excessively. Consumers can thus be protected from misleading information. Nutrient profiles are not meant as information for the end user and do not replace nor supplement nutritional labelling provisions.

The EU Commission has presented a draft regulation according to which the nutrients salt, sugar and saturated fatty acids are to be included in the nutrient profiles. BfR generally supports proposals by the EU Commission on nutrient profiles, yet some issues still require further discussion. The following Opinion provides BfR answers to questions of the Committee on Food, Agriculture and Consumer Protection.

The full version of this BfR Opinion is available in German on http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/208/bfr_beantwortet_fragen_des_ernaehrungsausschusses_des_deutschen_bundestages_zu_naehrwertprofilen.pdf